

CHARACTERIZATION OF AGRO BACTERIAL GROWTH AND ACTIVITY IN SUSPENSIONS USING OPTICAL TWEEZERS

Yogesha Lakkegowda *

Department of Physics, Government First Grade College, Tiptur-572 201 India.

Email: yogesh.bub@gmail.com

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Abstract

We discuss a method of measuring activity of bacteria of significance in agriculture using optical tweezer based technique. The hydrodynamic disturbance caused by collective bacterial activity results in the hike of measured power spectral densities of the thermally fluctuated trapped bead in active bacterial suspensions. Measurement of bacterial activity as a function of time is enabled us to identify bacterial strain which shows higher motility.

Introduction:

Microorganisms play a crucial role in agriculture. They also find utility in the production of many fermented food products, enzymes, beverages, etc. They are also used in industrial processes e.g. production of ethanol using *Sacharomyces cerevesiae* (1) and production of antibiotics and insecticides.

The mechanical properties of microorganisms in particular: bacterial suspensions are characterised earlier using different methods, viz., Sameer Al-Ashesh et al, showed that bacterial suspension's apparent viscosity increases with increase in biomass concentration and decrease of apparent viscosity of suspensions with increase in temperature by using viscometer(2). G.V. Soni et al, explained the method of measuring the dynamic viscosity of self-propelled active particles using an intensity modulated optical tweezer (3). Though optical tweezer is an important tool for these kind of measurements, enough care should be taken to avoid damage to bacterial cells by this method. For e.g., Rasmussen et al, investigated the degree of physiological damage to bacterial cells caused by optical trapping (4). Ericson et al, shown the influence of optical trapping methodology in elucidating the mechanism involved in stationary

phase induced bacterial death and population heterogeneity (5). We report here the growth and activity four bacterial strains at a temperature of $23.5 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ using optical tweezers.

Optical Tweezers:

The optical tweezer setup used by us has been described elsewhere [6]. Briefly, it consists of a collinear set of beams of a trapping (1064 nm) and detection laser (980 nm) guided into a 100x (1.4 NA) oil immersion objective on a custom made inverted microscope. The instrument is also equipped with a PZT stage and a quadrant photo detector (QPD) for laser beam detection, which in turn measures the position of the trapped particle. In this work, we have monitored the back scattering from the 980 nm laser, as our QPD had maximum sensitivity at this wavelength.

Figure 1: Dual optical trap – A schematic view

Bacterial strains:

Biofertilizers are specific beneficial microorganisms which are capable of supplying plant nutrients to soil-plant system by their biological activities. These microbes are designed to improve soil fertility and productivity which help plant growth by increasing the biological activity of derived microorganisms in the root environment. They are produced in the laboratory by depleting biotechnological methods. These methods are challenging aspect in scientific agriculture where in biological N_2 fixation, phosphate solubilization and mineralization of nutrients, transformation of elements to utilizable forms are made through. Some of the Biofertilizers which are investigated are detailed below.

Rhizobium : It is most extensively used as biofertilizer because of its proven ability to fix the atmospheric nitrogen by symbiosis with leguminous host plant. It is treated as seed treatment in pulses like gram, red gram, Bengal gram and in oil seeds like groundnut. Generally, in soils, the crop specific rhizobial population will be low in number, hence it is necessary to introduce

crop pertinently Rhizobia through seed treatment for maintaining effective rhizobial population in order to improve nodulation and nitrogen fixation.

Azospirillum brasillense: It is an aerocative, microaerophilic and diazotroph microorganism in which it is a potential nitrogen fixer in rice ecosystem under water logged condition and in sugarcane under controlled irrigated condition more efficient in crop growth & yield. This is also referred to as dual purpose bacteria with salinity tolerance.

Potassium mobilizer: The bacteria k-mobilizer is a gram negative motile rod type, aerobic acid tolerant and solid tolerant bacteria that survives at low temperatures ranges from 15°C and 42°C.

Pseudomonas fluorescens: It encompasses a group of common non pathogenic that colonizes soil, water and plant surface environments. It is a gram negative, chemoheterotrophic, motile rod shaped bacteria in which it produces soluble greenish fluorescent pigment. It grows well in mineral salt media supplemented with any large number of carbon source.

Preparation of bacteria suspension:

Overnight cultures of bacteria were diluted in sterilized media namely, (a) Medium 1; King's B medium, (b) Medium 2; Nutrient broth and (c) Medium 3; Potato dextrose broth detailed elsewhere (reference). The strains were then grown at 37°C for 6 hours, 12 hours, and 24 hours in all the three mediums. The well grown cultures were loaded inside a sample chamber made by O-ring (dia:10 mm, height: 2 mm) on a cover slip and about 1 to 2µl of 3 micron sized polystyrene beads were added and mixed uniformly. While making measurements, a constant distance of 30µm between trapped bead and cover slip is maintained to avoid surface effects.

Results and discussion:

Cell count determination using Haemocytometer

The growth of bacterial cells in different media compositions were measured using Haemocytometer. The concentration of the bacterial cells in the three mediums after time intervals of 6 hrs, 12hrs and 24 hrs is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Growth of bacterial cells in three media as a function time.

Figure 2 shows that growth of *P. fluorescens* in King's B medium initiates very quickly, while in Potato dextrose broth it initiates slowly, where as Nutrient broth lies in the middle. In addition, it is clear that *P. fluorescens* grows well in King's B medium than that in other two media.

Optical tweezer studies

About 20-25 sets of position information data of a thermally fluctuated trapped bead were recorded. For each set of data, Power Spectral Density (PSD) is calculated as explained in the theory by adjacent averaging 25 data points. The PSD data is then averaged over all the sets by normalization.

Figure 3: PSD of a trapped bead in three media at zero cell counts.

Figure 3 shows the (PSD) values of the trapped particles of same size embedded in three different mediums at zero concentration of bacteria. The three media, free from bacteria, show same corner frequency of the order of 37Hz.

Figure 4: PSD of a trapped bead in three media after (a) 6 hrs, (b) 12 hrs and (c) 24 hrs of growth of bacterial culture.

Figures 4 (a) – (c) shows the PSD values of *P. fluorescens* bacterial suspension in the three media after 6 hrs, 12 hrs and 24 hrs of bacterial culture growth at room temperature. A significant difference in the PSD values at three different media was noticed. The higher values of PSD at lower frequencies in King's b medium is due to the fast growth of bacterial culture in this medium and hence the effect of the collective bacterial activity raises the amplitude of the thermally fluctuating trapped bead and as a result PSD has higher values than that of Nutrient broth and Potato dextrose broth. The higher values of PSD data may be due to the hydrodynamic disturbances caused by the surrounding bacterial activity such as tumbling and swimming behavior of the bacteria. The tumbling and swimming action of the bacteria raise the amplitude of fluctuations of the trapped bead and hence the resulted PSD has higher values comparable with less collectively active bacterial suspensions. From the above PSD data and Bacterial cell counts data we may conclude that *P. fluorescens* grows well in King's B medium. Hence we can say that King's B medium is the best medium for *P. fluorescens* culture growth compared to Potato dextrose broth and nutrient broth.

Figure 5: PSD of Potassium mobilizer and Azospirillum brasillense bacterial suspension at different media.

In order to compare this with other bacterial culture, two other bacteria namely Potassium mobilizer and Azospirillum brasillense were subjected for further investigation. The PSD results are shown in figures 5(a) and 5(b). From the figures we can clearly say that Potassium

mobilizer grows well in specific media 1, whereas *Azospirillum brasillense* grows well in specific media 2.

In addition to understand bacterial activity of different bacterial strains as a function of time, we have defined the activity factor, which is the ratio of PSD of the bead in the presence of active bacterial cells to the PSD of the bead in the presence of inactive bacterial cells at the same cell counts.

Figure 6: Activity factor as a function of lag time for different bacterial cultures

As an extension of this, we have measured the bacterial activity for four kinds of bacteria viz., *P. fluorescens*, Potassium mobilizer, *Azospirillum brasillense* and *Rhizobium* grown in their native media at a concentration of 5×10^9 cells/ml. Figure 6 shows the value of activity factor as a function of lag time. We have observed a higher value of activity factor in case of Potassium mobilizer than that in other bacterial strains due to its higher motility. Hence we can conclude that Potassium mobilizer is a highly active strain at room temperature and other surrounding conditions.

Conclusion:

We have characterized the real time changes in bacterial growth under the action of different nutrients. Later, we have made a comparison study on motility of different genera of bacteria in their native media. We found that Potassium mobilizer is a highly active strain at room temperature.

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